

Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the implementation of the child identity card policy in Banjarbaru City which is implemented by the Department of Population and Civil Registration of Banjarbaru City based on the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 2 of 2016 on Child Identity Card.

The research method used by researcher is a qualitative method with descriptive qualitative research type and data sources come from primary and secondary data. The data collection techniques conducted by researcher are through observation, interviews, and documentation or collection of supporting documents. The data analysis techniques that researcher performed are data reduction, data presentation, and deduction from the data sources obtained. Meanwhile, to test the data validity, the researcher conducts triangulation namely comparing the data from interview results and collection of supporting documents.

The result shows that the Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City is implemented by socializing Child Identity Card, having cooperation with working partners and implementing issuance service of Child Identity Card. Nevertheless, in its implementation, it is still not said to be achieved properly in terms of the achievement of the issuance of Child Identity Card in Banjarbaru City which is still low. It is also seen from the utilization of the Child Identity Card itself; its usefulness has not been optimized because in the implementation of the Child Identity Card policy, which is implemented by the Department of Population and Civil Registration is lack of budget so that the implementation of the Child Identity Card program is not optimally implemented.

It is suggested for the Banjarbaru Government especially for the Department of Population and Civil Registration in Banjarbaru City can increase the priority of budget allocation for the Child Identity Card program, increasing advanced socialization of the CIC program in Banjarbaru City and taking the advantages of the output to be useful for children.

KEYWORDS: Policy Implementation, Child Identity Card.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries that is large in the growth of the population every year, so along with the increasing number of child births and following the latest technological developments. The form of government policy to serve, protect and prosper the community is to run a population administration that is comprehensive, structured and applicable nationally based on Law No. 24 of 2013 on Population Administration and refers to the new policy on Population Administration issued by the government through the Ministry of Home Affairs is The Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 2 of 2016 on Identity Cards. The child (KIA) is expected to be an identity card for the child. Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 2 of 2016, requires all children under the age of 17 to have a Child IDENTITY Card (KIA).

In the Implementation of this Child Identity Card (KIA) Program even though it has been introduced since 2016, but until now there are still many areas in South Kalimantan that are late in implementing Child IDENTITY Cards, one of which is in Banjarbaru City. Based on observations by looking at the results of recapitulation data on the daily report of population registration services in districts / cities of South Kalimantan Province sourced from the Report of the Office of Population and Civil Registration of South Kalimantan Province, obtained data recapitulation of the number of printing children's identity cards in South Kalimantan as of January 2020 amounted to 279,682 kia stamps printed. And for the realization of the city of Banjarbaru printed 9,274 blangko KIA, which is estimated to be only 10% of the number of children under 17 years old recorded through the number of ownerships of birth certificate residents in Banjarbaru city.

As for the problems for the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City, including:

1. Lack of socialization from the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City gradually and continuously about the implementation of KIA policies to stakeholders, implementers and the community.

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2. Regional budgets sourced from APBD (Regional Revenue and Spending Budget) and limited DAK (Special Allocation Funds) result in no maximum program when socializing constrained by operational costs in the field
3. Lack of innovation and initiative of officers in carrying out duties, especially responsibility in carrying out direct service duties to the community
4. The Child Identity Card (KIA) policy program was late to be implemented in Banjarbaru City which should have been done since 2016 but only implemented in April 2019.
5. The issuance of a birth certificate that is the basic requirement for printing a Child IDENTITY Card (KIA) is not achieved which has an impact on KIA policy cannot be done.
6. Existing budget constraints for KIA printing allocations.

On this occasion, researchers will discuss in depth how the process of implementing the Child Identity Card (KIA) policy in Banjarbaru City and what are the inhibiting factors in the implementation of the Child Identity Card policy in Banjarbaru City.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Government policy

In English it is referred to as "public policy". There are some experts who define policy in their own view, among others according to Thomas R. Dye (Wahab, 2015: 15) stated "whatever governments choose to do do dor or not to do". (The choice of any action taken or not to be taken by the government). According to Dye, if the government chooses to do something, then there is a purpose, because public policy is an "action" of the government. If the government chooses not to do something, it is also a public policy that certainly has a purpose. Eystone (Wahab, 2015:13) who formulated in a short way that public policy is "the relationship of governmental unit to its environment". (Between unit relationships that take place between units / units of government and their environment). Wilson (Wahab,2015:13) "The actions, objectives and pronouncements of governments on particular matters, the step the take (or fail to take) to implement them, and the explanations they give for what happens (or does not happen)". Anderson in Dwiyanto (2009: 17) defines policy as the behavior of a number of actors (officials, groups, government agencies) or a series of actions that have a specific goal that is followed and carried out by a person or group of perpetrators to solve a particular problem.

In another concept an expert named William N. Dunn in Parson (2006) said the process of public policy analysis is a series of intellectual activities carried out in the process of activities that are political in nature. Political activity is seen in a series of activities that include agenda preparation, policy formulation, policy adoption, policy implementation, and policy assessment. Korten (in The 2003:7) says that a policy is successfully determined by the relationship of three aspects, namely: 1) the type of policy, 2) the policy recipient and 3) the policy implementing organization. Policy implementing organizations must be able to formulate what is an expression of the needs of prospective policy recipients or target groups in a policy.

B. Policy Process

The stages of public policy according to William Dunn as quoted by Winarno (2007: 32-34) are as follows:

1. Agenda preparation stage

The elected and appointed officials put the issue on the public agenda. Previously this issue competed first to be included in the policy agenda. In the end, some issues got onto the policy agenda of the policy framers. At this stage it may be that a problem is not touched at all, while another problem is set to be the focus of discussion, or there is also a problem for some reason delayed for a long time.

2. Policy formulation stage

Issues that have made their thing onto the policy agenda are then discussed by policymakers. These problems are defined to then find the best solution. The problem solving comes from various alternatives or policy options (policy alternatives / policy options) that exist.

3. Policy adoption stage

Of the many policy alternatives offered by policy framers, ultimately one of those policy alternatives was adopted with the support of a legislative majority, a consensus between the directors of the institution or a judicial ruling.

4. Policy implementation stage

Van Meter and Van Horn (Wahab, 2015:135) present policy implementation as actions taken either by individuals / officials or government or private groups directed at achieving the goals outlined in policy decisions. Policy standards and objectives are based on interests.

5. Policy evaluation

In this stage the policies that have been implemented will be assessed or evaluated, to see the extent of the policies made to achieve the desired impact, namely solving the problems faced by the community.

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C. Policy Implementation

Implementation according to Pressman and Wildavsky in erwan and dyah (2015: 20), is interpreted by several keywords as follows: to carry out policies (to carry out) to fulfill the promises as stated in the policy document (to fulfill), to produce output as stated in the policy objectives (to produce), to complete the mission that must be realized in the policy objectives (to complete). Ripley and Franklin (Winarno, 2014:148) have the opinion that implementation is what happens after a law is established that gives program authority, policy, benefits, or a real type of output. Grindle (Winarno, 2014: 149) also gave his views on implementation by saying that in general, the task of implementation is to form a linkage that facilitates goals can be realized as a result of a government activity. Van Meter and Van Horn in Winarno (2007:102) define public policy implementation as actions taken by public organizations directed toward achieving the goals set out in previous decisions.

The process of implementing public policy is essentially an activity to distribute policy output carried out by implementers to policy goals in an effort to realize policy objectives. Policy objectives are expected to emerge when policy output can be well received by the target group and utilized properly. Implementation of the policy itself can only begin when public policy objectives have been established, programs have been created, and funds have been allocated for the achievement of the policy objectives.

D. Public Policy Implementation Models

Rational System Implementation (Top-Down)

According to Parsons (2006), it was this implementation model that first appeared. The top down approach has a view on the relationship of implementation policy as covered in Rousseau's Emile: "Everything is good if it is left in the hands of the Creator. Everything is bad in the hands of men." According to Parsons (2006), this rational model contains the idea that implementation is to get people to do what they are told and control the sequence of stages in a system. Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983) in Idris Patarai (2020), argue that top down implementation is the process of implementing fundamental policy decisions. Some of the experts who develop policy implementation models with a top down perspective are as follows:

- a. Van Meter dan Van Horn
- b. George Edward III
- c. Mazmanian dan Sabatier
- d. Model Grindle.

Implementation of Bottom-Up Policy

The implementation model with a bottom-up approach emerges as a criticism of the rational (top down) approach model. Parsons (2006), suggests that what really matters in implementation is the relationship between policymakers and policy implementers. The bottom-up model is a model that views the process as a negotiation and the formation of consensus. Still according to Parsons (2006), the bottom-up approach model emphasizes the fact that implementation on the ground provides flexibility in the implementation of policies.

E. Teori Implementasi Kebijakan

There are quite a number of policy implementation theories including:

Donald Van Metter and Carl Van Horn (1975)

According to Van Metter and Van Horn in Subarsono (2011: 99), there are five variables in influencing implementation performance, namely:

- 1) standards and objectives
- 2) Resources
- 3) Communication between organizations and strengthening of activities
- 4) Characteristics of the executing agent
- 5) Social conditions, political economy

Theory of George C. Edward III Theory

According to Edward III in Subarsono (2011:90), policy implementation is influenced by four variables, namely:

- 1) Communication
- 2) Resources
- 3) Disposition
- 4) Bureaucratic Structure

Theory of Merilee S. Grindle

Successful Implementation according to Grindle in Subarsono (2011: 93) is influenced by two major variables, namely: Policy content and implementation environment. Policy content variables include:

- 1) The extent to which the interests of the target group are contained in the content of the policy

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- 2) Types of benefits received by the target group
- 3) The extent of the desired change of a policy
- 4) Is the location of a program, right?
- 5) Has a policy mentioned the implementation of the tator in detail?
- 6) Is a program supported by adequate resources?

While policy environment variables include:

- 1) Most of the power, interests and strategies possessed by the actors involved in the implementation of the policy
- 2) Characteristics of institutions and regimes in power
- 3) Level of compliance and responsiveness of the target group

Theory of Ripley dan Franklin

According to Ripley and Franklin in Haedar Akib (2010), that to support the successful implementation of policies need to be based on three aspects, namely:

- 1) The level of bureaucratic compliance with the bureaucracy above it or the level of bureaucracy
- 2) There is a smooth routine and no problems
- 3) Implementation and the desired impact (benefits) of all targeted programs

But in this case researchers will focus on the theory according to George C Edward III.

F. Policy Implementation under the model of George C Edward III

Communication

According to Agustino (2006:157); "Communication is one of the important variables that influence the implementation of public policy, communication determines the success of achieving the objectives of public policy implementation" Edward III in Agustino (2006: 157-158), proposed three variables used in measuring communication success:

- 1) Transmission. Good communication will be able to produce a good implementation as well. Often there is a problem in the distribution of communication, namely the existence of misunderstanding (miscommunication) caused by the many levels of bureaucracy that must be passed in the communication process, so that what is expected is distorted in the middle of the road.
- 2) Clarity. The communication received by policy implementers (street-level-bureaucrats) should be clear and unsequiled or unambiguous.
- 3) Consistency. The orders given in the implementation of a communication must be consistent and clear to be established or executed. If the orders given often change, it can cause confusion for implementers in the field.

Resources

Edwards III in Widodo (2013) categorizes organizational resources consisting of: "Staff, information, authority, facilities; building, equipment, land and supplies". Edward III argued that such resources could be measured from aspects of their adequacy in which implied conformity and clarity; "Insufficient resources will mean that laws will not be enforced, services will not be provided and reasonable regulation will not be developed".

According to Edward III in Agustino (2006: 158-159), resources are important in the implementation of good policies. The indicators used to see the extent to which resources affect policy implementation consist of:

- 1) Staff. The main resources in policy implementation are staff or employees (street-level bureaucrats). Failures that often occur in the implementation of policies, one of which is caused by staff / employees who are not adequate, sufficient, or incompetent in their fields. Increasing the number of staff and implementors alone is not enough to solve the problem of policy implementation, but adequacy of staff with the necessary expertise and capabilities (competent and capable) in implementing policies.
- 2) Information. In policy implementation, information has two forms: first, information related to how to implement the policy. Second, information about compliance data from implementers to established government regulations and regulations.
- 3) Authority. In general, the authority must be formal in order for the order to be implemented effectively. Authority is the authority or legitimacy for implementers in carrying out politically established policies. When authority does not exist, the power of implementors in the public eye is not legitimized, so as to thwart the implementation of public policy. But in other contexts, when formal authority is available, there is often an error in the effectiveness of authority. On the one hand, the effectiveness of authority is required in the implementation of policies; But on the other hand, effectiveness will shrink when authority is perverted by the executor for his own or his group's benefit.
- 4) Facilities. Physical facilities are an important factor in policy implementation. Implementors may have sufficient staff, capable and competent, but without supporting facilities (facilities and infrastructure) then the implementation of the policy will not be successful.

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Disposition (Attitude of the executor)

According to Edward III in Winarno (2005:142-143) it is "that tendencies or dispositions are one of the factors that have important consequences for effective policy implementation". Factors of concern to Edward III in Augustine (2006:159) regarding dispositions in policy implementation consist of:

- 1) The appointment of bureaucracy will pose real obstacles to policy implementation if existing personnel do not implement the policies desired by the upper officials. Therefore, the appointment and selection of policy implementing personnel must be people who have dedication to the policies that have been set, more specifically to the interests of the citizens.
- 2) Incentives are one of the suggested techniques to overcome the problem of policy implementers' attitudes by manipulating incentives. Basically, people move based on their own interests, so manipulating incentives by policymakers influences the actions of policy implementers. By adding to certain profits or costs will probably be a driving factor that makes the executors run the order well. This is done as an effort to fulfill personal or organizational interests.

Bureaucratic Structure

According to Edwards III in Winarno (2005: 150) there are two main characteristics of bureaucracy: "Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) and fragmentation". "Standard operational procedure (SOP) is a development of internal demands for certainty of time, resources and uniformity needs in a complex and broad work organization" (Winarno, 2005:150). The basic size of sops or work procedures is commonly used to cope with common conditions in various public and private sectors. By using SOPs, implementers can optimize the time available and can serve to uniformize the actions of officials in complex and widespread organizations, resulting in great flexibility and great similarity in the application of regulations.

Based on the results of Edward III's research summarized by Winarno (2005: 152) explained that: "SOPs are very likely to be an obstacle to the implementation of new policies that require new ways of working or new types of personnel to implement policies. That way, the greater the policy requires changes in the ways that are prevalent in an organization, the greater the probability of sops hindering implementation."

The second nature of the bureaucratic structure that is influential in the implementation of policy is fragmentation. Edward III in Winarno (2005: 155) explains that "fragmentation is the spread of the responsibility of a policy to several different bodies that require coordination". In general, the greater the coordination required to implement a policy, the less likely the program or policy success is. Fragmentation resulted in narrow views of many bureaucratic institutions. This will have adverse primary consequences for the successful implementation of the policy.

G. Child IDENTITY Card Policy

Kia issuance is an embodiment of the state's presence in improving public quality, because kia that will be owned by every Indonesian child in addition to will be a valid identification or self-proof for children, especially will also make children able to perform public services independently and meet their needs easily, quickly and cheaply, among others in educational activities, health or other social activities.

The basic constitution of the implementation of the Child Identity Card (KIA) includes:

1. Pay attention to the results of the International Convention on the Rights of the Child that has been ratified by the Government of Indonesia, and pay attention to the provisions stipulated in Article 27 of Law No. 35 of 2014 on Amendments to Law No. 23 of 2002 on Child Protection
2. Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration as amended by Law No. 24 of 2013, mandates that in accordance with Article 13
3. Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 2 of 2016.

III. METHOD

This research is carried out with a qualitative approach that is data spelled out with words, where numbers are used only as support. Thus the research report will contain data excerpts that to give an overview of the presentation of the report then analyze the problem so that it can become a comprehensive scientific work related to the Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City. This type of research is Descriptive, Descriptive was chosen because the researchers considered very appropriate and also appropriate to describe the reality or phenomenon that researchers managed to find in the field regarding the implementation of the Implementation of The Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City was carried out by the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City. The reason for choosing Banjarbaru City as a research locus is because researchers as residents in Banjarbaru City so it is necessary to examine phenomena related to the implementation of kia programs in Banjarbaru City with focus and easy access to data in this study. Banjarbaru city is a strategic area in South Kalimantan that has human resources and higher education level than other districts / cities in South Kalimantan. The research instrument is the researcher itself who will dig up the results of research from informants through interviews, field observations and documentation with tools in the form of field records, videos and photos from data obtained to analyze communication, resources, dispositions or attitudes

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of implementers and bureaucratic structures in research on the implementation of child identity card (KIA) policies in Banjarbaru City.

In this study, the party who will be used as an informant is a person who is considered to have information and can provide knowledge, the widest experience related to the Implementation of child identity card policies in the city of Banjarbaru that are needed by researchers in the field. What will be used as a key informant and supporting informant by researchers is:

- 1) Head of Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City,
- 2) Head of Population Registration in the Office of Population and Civil Registration..

Supporting Informants:

- 1) Operator / Staff of the Office of Population and Civil Registration
- 2) Banjarbaru Community

The data in this study is primary data and secondary data. Primary data includes basic data related directly to research obtained from observations and interviews with informants, including the Head of Population and Civil Registration Office and head of population registration services to obtain data and information related to research. Secondary data sources include research support data sourced from books, regulations, documentation, archives, letters and reports of activities and news in the implementation of the issuance of a Child Identity Card (KIA) in the city of Banjarbaru that has relevance to research. Research Techniques use observation methods, interviews and documentation.

Data analysis used is a descriptive method of analytics, which describes the data collected in the form of words, images, and not numbers. Data derived from manuscripts, interviews, field records, documents, and so on, is then described so as to provide clarity on reality or reality (Sugiyono, 2014: 88). Data analysis in qualitative research is carried out from before entering the field, during the field and after completion in the field. According to Bogdan & Biklen (in Gunawan, 2016: 223) Analysis conducted in the field is carried out continuously, while the data is collected, is an effort to solidify the data as the final data analysis material before the researcher leaves the field.

IV. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Process of Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City

The Office of Population and Civil Registry of Banjarbaru City in its implementation by:

- 1) Socializing the KIA Program, which is based on the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 2 of 2016 on Child Identity Cards as well as following up on the Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs number 471.13-257/Dukcapil 2018 concerning the determination of districts / cities implementing the issuance of Child Identity Cards in 2018.

From the results of the study both interviews with sources and from secondary data found that indeed in 2019 the relevant agencies had carried out socialization including in collaboration with the PKK Subdistrict and Organization, but the socialization did not continue due to budget constraints.

If it is associated with the theory put forward by George C. Edward III then researchers find the following facts:

Communication

From the transmission variables it was found that the communication carried out in socialization was going well, the clarity of communication was sufficient, as well as the consistency conveyed by the relevant officials both because it was in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, it was just necessary to make some improvements because they understood the policy.

Resources

From the results of the study found that in the Population and Civil Records Office of Banjarbaru City, there was a lack of human resources and lack of budget availability that caused socialization not to run optimally.

Disposition

Indicators of bureaucratic appointment and incentives are indicators that exist in disposition, namely with kia program socialization activities charged to the Field of Population Registration Services as coordinators assisted by the joint team of KIA program socialization, in its implementation there are no special incentives given for the implementation of KIA program socialization, there is only honor of socialization sources and there is already honor of Additional Income Allowance (TTP) and PPTK honor for officials. technical implementation of activities.

- 2) Cooperate with partners, in the implementation of the Child Identity Card policy. In this case, the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City cooperates with cross-regional device work structures (SKPD) and work units in the Banjarbaru City government, private parties and community institutions.

The cooperation of partners carried out by the Office of Population and Civil Registration in implementing the Child Identity Card (KIA) policy in Banjarbaru City is to assign several tasks to partners, one of which is the Education Office with the

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target of policy objects to schools and is considered quite effective in achieving the target of participants who are in school age.

Communication

If associated with the theory of Policy Implementation according to Edward III, it can be concluded that indicators of Communication with Transmission, Clarity and Consistency have been carried out in carrying out cooperation with partners that have been carried out both by conducting effective and efficient coordination with partners within the internal scope of SKPD and across sectors to support and implement the Child Identity Card policy in Banjarbaru City.

Resources

According to the theory of the implementation of Edward III's policy, the resource factor in the authority indicator has been implemented quite well, this is seen from the authority to carry out the cooperation built by the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City with partners with the implementation of duties to help the implementation of KIA program policies.

Disposition

It can be concluded that the disposition indicator or attitude of the implementer in Edward III theory that is established between leading sectors to partners who are committed to accepting well the tasks given in accordance with existing instructions and directions to help implement the Child Identity Card program with indicators of bureaucratic appointments appointing teams in collaboration with the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City has been implemented properly.

3) Performing services for issuing a Child Identity Card (KIA)

Based on data obtained from the PIAK Section of the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City, data obtained that shows children aged (0-17) years who are recorded as residents of Banjarbaru City amounted to 78,892 people and who already have a birth certificate which is the basic requirement to print KIA amounting to 73,120 people, with the realization of the number of KIA prints until the first quarter of 2021 amounting to 24,372 children. The implementation of the Child Identity Card program in Banjarbaru City has been implemented since April 2019 with the realization of more than 20% of the number of children who have Birth Certificates in Banjarbaru City as a reference to the basic target of the National Child Identity Card (KIA) program set by the Ministry of Home Affairs in the strategic plan and work plan set for the district / city government. Based on data recapitulation of Printing Of Children's Identity Cards obtained by researchers sourced from the PIAK section, the researcher concluded that in the implementation of the Child Identity Card policy in Banjarbaru City is still very minimal in the issuance of KIA printing because there are still approximately 54,520 children who do not have KIA. Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by researchers found that the delay in implementing the Child Identity Card (KIA) policy that should have been implemented in 2016 could only be implemented in 2019 which became the dominant factor in the slow realization of KIA issuance.

Communication

From the results of the study it was obtained that the communication variable through transmission indicators runs quite well, because the information conveyed is on target. From the indicator of clarity of information, the author values quite well because it is not only delivered directly but also indirectly through media such as websites, banners and others, and from the aspect of consistency, services are carried out in accordance with the provisions of the laws and regulations.

Resources

Based on the results of human resources research (staff) in terms of readiness, professional dedication skills, competence, number of human resources, it can be concluded that human resources are an important factor for the implementation of policies well where in the implementation of service officers, the Population And Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City is quite good, although there are shortcomings in terms of the number of human resources. Budget indicators already exist even though it is not enough to complete the KIA program. Based on budget allocation data for the implementation of KIA in Banjarbaru City, researchers assessed that kia program budget in the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City is still very minimal considering based on the recapitulation of issuance realization. Facilities in the issuance of Children's Identity Cards (KIA) in the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City already have a comfortable space for all employees / operators with computers and air-conditioned rooms, technically already have printer tools and special printing tools KIA brand Evolis Avansia and Evolis Primasy to provide KIA services already have a good network system, although there is a network disruption, so that it has an impact on employee performance because they cannot work, it is expected that with the purchase of the Mandiri Population Administration (ADM) platform tool is able to accelerate the performance process of KIA services.

Disposition

The disposition indicator or attitude of the implementer in Edward III theory to carry out kia issuance services by the executor is well committed with honesty, integrity and work ethic in carrying out the tasks given in accordance with the

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instructions and directions available to carry out the services of issuing the Child Identity Card program and indicators of bureaucratic appointment at the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City have been carried out properly by appointing the Apparatus in accordance with the with competence and professionalism in their fields in accordance with the mandate in the Laws and Regulations.

Bureaucratic Structure

According to Edward III in Nugroho (2009), explained that the bureaucratic structure is concerned with the suitability of bureaucratic organizations that are organizers of public policy implementation. The challenge is how not to occur bureaucratic fragmentation because this structure makes the implementation process far from effective. In the Implementation of The Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City, researchers divided the explanation of the results about the bureaucratic structure into 2 (two) indicators of sop bureaucratic structure, and in the Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City is quite good seen from the sop aspect that has contained the duties and responsibilities of each implementer of the Child Identity Card Policy. This means that the complete SOP on the implementation of the Child Identity Card Policy (KIA in Banjarbaru City). The next indicator is fragmentation. Indicators of fragmentation in the division of information delivery service tasks to the community, services and issuance of KIA researchers see it is good enough in accordance with the duties and responsibilities given to subordinates, because it already has a clear SOP in terms of the implementation of the Child Identity Card Policy (KIA) program in Banjarbaru City.

5.2.2 Analysis of Factors Inhibiting the Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy (KIA) in Banjarbaru City

Based on the results of the discussion above, researchers can conduct a general analysis of factors inhibiting the Implementation of Child Identity Card Policy (KIA) in Banjarbaru City which in this case the Population and Civil Registry Office of Banjarbaru City as the Leading Sector still finds obstacles because the main factor is budget constraints that have no maximum impact on all programs carried out, among others:

1. Limited socialization activities are only carried out in 2019 and there is no continued face-to-face socialization directly to the community which indicates that socialization activities are not optimal and uneven because there are still many people in Banjarbaru City who do not know and have KIA when viewed from the results of kia issuance recapitulation.
2. Delays in implementing the KIA program, due to the achievement of the issuance of Birth Certificates that have not been achieved become the main requirement in the issuance of KIA, then the inhibition factor of budget readiness is large enough for the procurement of blangko, printing press and ink, so that it can only implement it in 2019 in Banjarbaru City which has an impact on the late achievement of KIA issuance in Banjarbaru City.
3. The Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City has not committed and cooperated in the utilization of the KIA program because it has not optimized the utilization of KIA which is an important point that must be implemented in accordance with orders from the Minister of Home Affairs, so that the output of KIA issuance has not had benefits that can be felt by the community and children in particular.
4. Sum is limited in manpower (Staff) and must double duty due to budget constraints because there is no special budget to be able to recruit additional experts and special personnel to handle KIA policies. This has an impact on the realization of the realization of the issuance of Children's IDENTITY Cards in Banjarbaru City which is too late considering that there are still many 17-year-old residents of Banjarbaru City who do not have KIA.
5. The limitations of APBD (Regional Revenue and Spending Budget) budget and the absence of special allocation funds from the central government which is very important to realize the achievement of the target of issuing Children's Identity Cards in Banjarbaru City indicates that the KIA program is not a top priority of the Banjarbaru City Government because it is given a minimal budget.

CONCLUSSION

Based on the results of research and discussion analysis that have been outlined in the previous chapters, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- 1) The process of Implementing the Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City has been carried out quite well can be seen from the implementation process by implementing the Kia Program Socialization although not yet thoroughly, Collaborating with Partners and providing KIA issuance services by achieving the national target of 20% kia printing by 2020, but there are still 75% of children in Banjarbaru City who have KIA and KIA Utilization is not optimal because the city government Banjarbaru has not implemented kia utilization with third parties so that children who have KIA have not received the benefits of KIA to get public services in Banjarbaru City.
- 2) Inhibiting factors in the Implementation of The Child Identity Card Policy in Banjarbaru City in general are the main factors that are the limitations of the allocation of funds / budgets available at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Banjarbaru City which has a major influence in the implementation of the Child Identity Card program.

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